

THE PHILOSOPHICAL CONCEPT OF FREEDOM BY J.-P. SARTRE

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ABSTRACT

The problem of freedom has always been the most significant and complex in the history of philosophical reflection.

At first glance, a person needs a certain freedom, with the help of which it is possible to show their abilities through physical and spiritual principles. Such concepts as democracy and humanism cannot be implemented without the participation of each individual.

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Today, it is customary to see a person as a bearer of rights and freedoms; someone who is able to independently create material and spiritual benefits, fill his spiritual world with new cultural achievements.

However, there is currently a crisis in public life. The development of Science and technology has negatively affected the formation of society. Even in the modern era, it was observed that the desire of man to subordinate nature to his goals led to an exploitative attitude not only to nature, but even to people; the pragmatic mind of man everywhere seeks benefits.

The role of Education inexorably falls with the refusal of people to critically comprehend the world around them, to find their place in it. A person, perceiving scientific achievements as truth, does not take into account the historical context of the development of science, does not think about the possible consequences of its discoveries, and does not evaluate all this from a morally humane position. The whole culture, along with philosophy, has become an industry of vulgarity, as a result of which individual freedom dies.

These difficulties force us to return to philosophical problems, among which the question of human freedom is far from the last place. French existentialism in the twentieth century actively investigated the problem of freedom.

Sartre's popularity as a philosopher is inseparable from his popularity as a writer, playwright and public figure. It should be noted that his multilateral activities are cemented by his philosophical beliefs and cannot be understood in isolation from them. Thus, the success of the first literary works, a distinctive feature of which is their richness of philosophical ideas, attracted the attention of the general public to the author's philosophical concept.

Sartre's role in modern French philosophy is determined primarily by the fact that he is the creator and the most prominent representative of a very influential trend — atheistic existentialism, represented by such thinkers as Albert Camus, Maurice Merleau-Ponty, Simone de Beauvoir, Francis Janson.

Jean-Paul Sartre's philosophical concept of freedom is based on the idea that a person is always free to choose his own path in life. He believed that a person remains free even in the most limited conditions, since he always has the opportunity to choose and take responsibility for his actions. This concept reflects his idea of "existence before the essence", where a person's existence is determined by his own choices and actions, and not by external factors.

The concept of "freedom" is ambiguous and multilateral. Freedom can be personal, social, moral, or political. The problem of freedom causes interesting disputes, philosophical debates on the topic of freedom have not stopped for two thousand years, but the problem is still unresolved. The problem of freedom often causes interesting debates and philosophical discussions.

The concept of freedom is complex and multifaceted, encompassing the ideas of individual freedom, autonomy, and free will. People have been asking questions about the nature of freedom for centuries, exploring its ethical, political, and social implications. From the point of view of different philosophical and cultural traditions, the meaning of freedom can vary greatly. This diversity of views adds richness and depth to the ongoing conversation about freedom and its role in human life.

Therefore, our goal is to consider some aspects of freedom that are important for a person. Hence, the main attention will be paid to human (personal) freedom. Since a person is a subject of his own life, a person actively builds the conditions of his life and his attitude to it. But creating herself and her life, she very often tries to escape from the will, she does not live authentically, or in dishonesty, according to the terminology of the famous French existentialist philosopher J.-P. Sartre. Therefore, Sartre considered it his task to free people from dishonesty and help them accept responsibility. In its developed form, freedom is responsible, and responsibility is free, and they act as a single mechanism of self-regulated arbitrary activity inherent in a

mature person. Without having inner freedom, a person cannot be a full-fledged person and be responsible for their actions.

Human existence, according to Sartre, is a continuous self-denial. His concept of freedom is the key to his entire worldview, both in his theoretical constructions and in his practical conclusions. All anthropocentricity revolves around this concept, as if on its axis, while self-centered, philosophy of existentialism. Sartre believed that a person decides for himself what he will be like, and is responsible for his actions and choices. He believed that an important part of human existence is freedom of choice and responsibility for this choice. Sartre argued that a person is opposed to the situation in which he finds himself, and through his choices retains his individuality.

The affirmation of freedom as an unconditional principle means a break with determinism, rationalism, and an objectively scientific understanding of reality. Freedom is interpreted by Sartre in the spirit of ending indeterminism. Freedom puts a person outside of regularity and causal dependence. It expresses a metaphysical gap with necessity both in its objectively materialistic understanding and in its logical necessity. Freedom does not tolerate cause or reason. Freedom is not recognized as the ability of a person to act in accordance with what he is, because his freedom itself is the choice of his being, a person as he freely chooses himself. The present is not in a natural connection with the past, but the past with the present. Freedom imposes independence on relations with the past, denial of it, breaking with it. "Freedom is a human existence that takes its past out of the game ...»[1,65].

According to Sartre, no objective circumstance can deprive a person of his freedom. The latter remains in any situation and is expressed in the ability to choose-to choose not real opportunities, but your attitude to this situation. Thus, the concept of freedom is consistently subjectivized by Sartre, reduced to the attitude of the subject to an independent circumstance. His independence, in fact, lies in how he perceives his addiction: he can "freely" come to terms with it, while he is just as free as rejecting it, standing against it. The prisoner or slave is free, self-determining his attitude to his situation. Moreover, the objective situation does not in itself restrict or suppress our freedom, but only to the extent that we feel it as a restriction, see it as an obstacle. After all, the obstacle, the restriction is determined by what we wanted. It is enough to give up your desire, and this situation will cease to be an obstacle. A consistent conclusion from Sartre's absolutized concept of freedom would be the motto: the task is not to change the world, but to change one's attitude to it [2,575].

The category of "freedom", as we see it, is contrasted with Sartre's necessity, and is not based on the latter. The theological aspect of this category, the purposefulness of freedom, breaks away from its causal definitions. Motives, aspirations, and ideals are not considered as a subjective refraction of causes, objective trends, and patterns. The future projected by consciousness, rather than the real present, serves as a criterion for freedom. Moreover, this future is taken out of connection with the possibility of its transformation

into reality. Freedom is rejected by the choice of a goal and does not require its achievement.

Sartre's subjective idealism reveals to us as subjectivist voluntarism: "... All barriers, all borders are destroyed by the consciousness of my freedom." Hence, freedom in Sartre acts as the only justification for human existence. The philosopher believes that man is free because he is never Immobile, defined by being, but is separate from it, he is not "in himself", but in the presence of himself. The person who is what he is can never be free. "Freedom is precisely nothing that is in the very essence of man, forcing human reality to make itself, instead of being ... Being for a person means choosing yourself ... Therefore, simple being is the being of man, that is, the non-existence of his being"[2,608].

This interpretation of freedom follows from the existential understanding of consciousness as "nothing." Irreducible from nothing, running away from things, representing pure spontaneity, consciousness is "not being, but the non-existence of being." Freedom is not a property of "being - for - yourself", it does not have freedom, but is freedom. "... "Freedom and being-for-yourself," Sartre argues, "are the same thing." Man is freedom. Such freedom is boundless, always equal to itself and not determined by anything. It is equally infinite in everyone.

Human action, Sartre writes, is absolutely Free, that is, it is carried out "without a fulcrum." If my body is included in the world, he explains, and is thus drawn into the chain of causes, then my consciousness is free, and this free manifestation is identical with existence. "A person cannot be either free or a slave, he is either always and completely free, or he is not at all." But such freedom is not, according to Sartre, an active, life-affirming force, it is full of pessimism. We are condemned to be free ... we are "thrown" into freedom [3,297].

However, while remaining largely in the position of calm voluntarism, Sartre cannot fail to recognize certain circumstances that limit the actions of our individual freedom. This shows its inconsistency, as well as the uncertainty of the interpretation of "being - in - yourself". In fact, Sartre argues, a person is never completely isolated: despite his freedom, he is included by the very fact of his birth in social life, in a specific era, with the fate of the nation, the class. "I am not 'free' to escape the fate of my class, my nation, my family, or even increase my power or wealth, nor to overcome my petty passions and habits. The story of every life as it is is a story of defeat. The hostility factor is such that it takes years of patience to achieve a minor result. Again, it is necessary to obey nature in order to possess it, that is, to insert my action into the network of determinism. Much more than it seems that a person "makes himself", he is made by climate and land, race and class, language, the history of the collective to which he belongs, heredity, the specific circumstances of his childhood, acquired habits, big and small events of his life " [5,659].

The fundamental capacity of man for freedom finds its influence in the fact that in fact we, mostly without noticing it, choose, affirm by our own decision

even what is once and for all given to us by a separate course of events and does not seem to need any subjective support from our side. Paradoxically, people do choose their own origin and Homeland, Love, suffering and death, often demonstrating their true spiritual world in this cross-section of self-determination. They choose, while at the same time choosing for themselves - thus building their own world, so that in it this ontological conditionality of their existence does not look like a wall of randomness, it acquires a deep content [7,273].

It is obvious, however, that the choices we make during our lives depend on the goals we set for ourselves, on the hierarchy of values we accept. Since our goals guide our choices, their free choice entails the freedom of all our actions. But how do we choose our goals? Existentialists claim that the choice of our goals is absolutely free, it is made without a fulcrum: each person freely sets the norms of the present, the beautiful, the majestic. Human emotions and passion are also free: they, like volitional acts, are certain subjective relationships through which we want to achieve the goals set by the free choice of my self.

Thus, freedom is a key aspect of human existence that is essential for every human being. Some aspects of freedom that may be particularly important to a person:

1. Freedom of speech: the ability to freely express one's thoughts and views is an important component of human freedom. This helps develop ideas, encourages discussions, and promotes open exchange of information.

2. freedom of choice: the ability to choose your own path of life, profession, faith and other aspects is

an important part of everyone's freedom. This allows each person to feel autonomous and independent.

3. Freedom from harassment: an important component of freedom is the ability to be protected from any form of harassment and discrimination. Everyone deserves respect for their rights and freedoms without any restrictions.

These aspects of freedom play an important role in the formation and development of each individual, providing an opportunity to freely express themselves and realize their potential.

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